

PROBLEMS OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBALIZATION

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Annotation: The article is dedicated to the matter of globalization process' influence at the modern education. According to the author's words, the development of globalization process in the educational area and necessity in rise of university graduate's competitiveness demands the higher education system's modernization in the direction of world's standard. At the same time, it's necessary to save the balance in modern conditions: being integrated to worldwide education's space, we should save the advantages of our own educational system.

Аннотация: Статья посвящена вопросу влияния процесса глобализации на современное образование. Как отмечает автор, развитие глобализационных процессов в сфере образования и объективная необходимость повышения конкурентоспособности выпускников вузов требуют модернизации системы высшего образования в направлении соответствия мировым стандартам. Вместе с тем, в современных условиях необходимо сохранить определенный баланс: интегрируясь в мировое образовательное пространство, следует сохранить достоинства собственной системы образования.

Key words: globalization, education, integration, modernization, globalization process.

Twenty first century has become the century of globalization for the world community. The process of globalization has significantly affected a very wide range of phenomena in the sphere of economics, politics, sociology, and education. Globalization is a process of worldwide economic, political, and cultural integration

and unification. This is an objective process that is systemic in nature, covering all spheres of society. As a result of globalization, the world is becoming more dependent on all its subjects. Globalization in its modern manifestation appears as a multi-level and multilateral system of various integration manifestations. The main ones are undoubtedly global communication, global economy, global politics, global culture, global science, global language, and global way of life.

Of course, globalization processes have had a significant impact on education. One of the most important elements of the globalization of education can be considered the informatization of society, which is characterized by the rapid development of computer and information technologies. Thanks to modern information technologies, the educational process began to take on qualitatively new forms. The globalization process has opened up the broadest prospects for all students who have the opportunity to receive any information online, remotely participate in conferences, webinars, use books from world libraries, and materials from the best scientific articles. The Internet has become one of the most important resources for obtaining information for students, teachers, as well as for a wide range of people wishing to change their profession or get additional education in a particular field. Today, you can get an education remotely.

While at home, in another city, in another country, you can listen to interesting lectures, watch master classes, video lessons. In addition, with the help of the Internet, it has become possible for people who cannot attend educational institutions for health reasons to receive an education. New technologies make it possible to solve such an important problem as visualization, clarity in the learning process. The Internet and other new technologies make it possible to make the educational process continuous. A person who has received an education replenishes his stock of knowledge virtually throughout his entire future life. Another important aspect of the development of globalization and its impact on education is related to the fact that globalization has literally opened the national borders of states, making it possible to receive an education in another country.

Currently, the largest universities in the world teach a large number of foreign students. Developing international cooperation, higher and secondary educational institutions provide for the exchange of students and teachers. The active implementation of the globalization process in the educational process is associated not only with positive aspects, but also has a number of serious problems that significantly complicate the integration of countries into the global educational space. Such obstacles to the problem of globalization of education include the language barrier. The majority of university students do not speak foreign languages. As a result, students cannot participate in conferences held in a foreign language; obtaining information from foreign sources is very problematic for some students; students cannot publish their work.

The student and teacher must have a high level of computer literacy. A person who does not know how to work with a computer becomes effectively cut off from new global educational opportunities. There is another problem of the globalization of education, which is increasingly being discussed by physiologists and doctors. The intensification of education, the use of computers entail health problems. This factor is especially significant for schoolchildren.

Another obvious risk of globalization is the destruction of the achievements of the national educational system. Having abandoned the formation of a holistic picture of the world in school and university graduates (who were previously capable of solving a variety of problems), we are preparing a "qualified consumer" who can work mainly according to instructions, but is not capable of creative thinking [1, P.256]. The so-called traditional teaching, which has been widely used recently, the origins of which go back to the ancient Greek Plato's Academy and Aristotle's Lyceum, has hundreds of years of experience, during which the techniques and methods of conducting lectures and seminars were honed and perfected. Since ancient times, students and teachers, pupils and teachers have tried to find the best forms of interaction in the learning process, which were embodied in a two-member combination: teacher-student audience, bright author's lectures-seminars, discussions, debates in which the entire

student group participates. What are the risks associated with abandoning traditional forms of conducting classes and the widespread passion for computer technologies? Modern learning processes often represent the practice of collecting and accumulating electronic texts.

By appropriating electronic information, presenting it as electronic property, acquiring it without much effort, the student passively accumulates it, collects knowledge, without interacting, without collaborating with the teacher. Undoubtedly, such a practice of accumulating information has certain advantages, which come down to saving time, to the clarity of educational material, the availability of necessary materials. At the same time, the passive accumulation of knowledge, characteristic of the globalization of education, gives rise to the effect of psychological indifference of students in the creation of knowledge systems. The negative influence of the ideology of globalization is also manifested in destructive changes in the direction and quality of the educational process.

The exclusion of the educational component from the educational process and its concentration on narrow professional goals contributes to the reorientation of students' consciousness to the satisfaction of utilitarian needs, puts consumer values and demands at the forefront. A cult of material well-being is formed, attitudes are formed towards the obligatory connection of professional work with enrichment and commercial success. But, as G. Marcuse showed, consumer values, turning into the basis of social integration, produce the effect of closing the cultural space, losing its spiritual dimension, as a result of which a type of "one-dimensional person" is formed [2, P.174]. The ideal to which education should strive, from the point of view of national interests (in order of priority) and the interests of national security, is a spiritual and moral person, a patriot, a citizen, a highly qualified specialist [2, P.174].

As K.D. Ushinsky noted, the nature and direction of public education are "a product of the long historical development of a nation, which cannot be borrowed from other peoples" [3, P.27]. The role of past cultural experience and the inertia of cultural processes cannot be underestimated. In the public mentality and the mentality of

society, as applied to a given generation, there are always those elements that were produced by past generations of people. At the same time, the individual mentality of people living today does not always reflect the priorities of the mentality of only the society that exists synchronously with these specific people. Therefore, the invasion of foreign cultural educational models poses a serious danger from the point of view of the effectiveness of socio-cultural reproduction. Thus, the development of globalization trends in the field of education, along with the objective need to increase the competitiveness of the economy and the human potential of society, unconditionally require the modernization of the paradigm, content, economic and institutional organization of education in the direction of compliance with world and European standards.

Thus, the globalization of education, reflected in the creation of a single educational space, is aimed not at creating contradictions in existing educational systems, but at coordinating their actions. In conclusion, I would like to note that the process of globalization is irreversible, and the educational space of the Commonwealth countries must inevitably integrate into the world educational space. The dialectical principle that is important to implement here is that the denial of the old by the new must be carried out not through destruction, as was often the case in the post-Soviet space, but through continuity, through the introduction of innovations based on traditional methods of teaching and education.

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